

DELIVERABLE OF YOUTUBE PLATFORM AS A COMMERCIAL HEALTH AWARENESS COMMUNICATION TO MALAYSIAN TRAVELER

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ABSTRACT

YouTube video search is the number one source of views in aggregation, the related video recommendation is the main source of views for most of the videos on YouTube. Health awareness also significant to economic progress, as healthy population live longer and will be increasingly productivity. Positive mental and physical health is a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully and can contribute to his or her community. In addition, our results reveal that there is a strong correlation between the view count of a video and the average view count of its top referrer videos. The aim of this study are to know the impacts of YouTube as a health awareness video to traveler from Malaysia, and also to find out factors of usage of YouTube rather than other medium applications . Besides that, the factors and the impact of usage is influencing the YouTube as a main website popular and the most websites trending in the worldwide. Health awareness is very crucial information that each person needs to know to ensure that they can maintain a better and healthier life. This study conducted out of 68 respondents where is 35 of female and 33 of male. Most of respondents are in range 15 to 45 years old that are users of new media platforms especially YouTube and interact frequently on these platforms. The questionnaire is made up of three major sections which collect data on the respondents' demographic profile, their exposure to YouTube, and their knowledge about health awareness video. As the result, this study showed that YouTube as a main platform to find any precautions about health awareness video or materials. In the meanwhile, the researcher agrees personally that YouTube is the best place to look for any videos or materials on health awareness precautions. With this study, it is made evident that YouTube's effects as a health awareness film for travelers from Malaysia altered a respondent's willingness to agree with the study's objectives

KEYWORDS

Health communication, Digital Media, Awareness, Future education, behaviour

1. INTRODUCTION

Health communication is a must knowledge among people on this day. Going through the assemble of new technology and the way of deliver the messages. The health communication information related for the recent years have been leading by both professionals and laymen that passes from platform social media and video assemble. According Horváth et. all in 2022 had overview about the purpose of communication through online platform that can present in

systematic health-related information that contains texts, audio and video-based to educate the other people. Nowadays, people from all over the world have been using YouTube at least once in their whole lives. It may be for education or entertainment. Basically, video deliverable in social media give different perspective and provide audiences guidance and present the practicality. According to Miller (2011), it has of course continued growth at dizzying rates, but it has also changed in terms of its business model, its interfaces, its cultural role, and the extent to which it regulates content and behavior since the past ten years. The development of media in the form of learning videos uploaded on the YouTube channel is expected to be able to provide solutions. Apart from being a medium of entertainment and news, YouTube can also be a source for learning (N. Chintalapati and V. S. K. Daruri, 2017)

Students involved in research have an advantage thanks to YouTube because it makes it simple for them to get the information. The majority of students used online resources to get information, with 78% turning to YouTube as their main source for anatomy-related video clips. These results imply that integrating social media into blended learning strategies in anatomy courses may be beneficial to the academic anatomy community. In addition to enabling for academic and ethical monitoring regarding the usage of internet video snippets whose provenance may not otherwise be known, this will ensure continuing contact with the YouTube generation of students (Barry, Marzouk et. al, 2015). In addition, since its founding in February 2005, YouTube has swiftly become the most widely used video site on the planet. Users visit YouTube to find, view, and share original video content. YouTube offers a platform for global video content engagement and serves as a distribution channel for content producers. Millions of users watch over a billion videos on YouTube every day, and each minute, users submit more than 24 hours of video there (Davidson, Liebold, Liu, Nandy and Vleet, 2010).

For each person to keep a better and healthier life, health awareness is highly important information that they must know. Enabling individuals to acquire practical knowledge that can aid in illness prevention is the major goal of raising awareness of the significance of health. In other words, health awareness campaigns should focus on spreading the message that prevention is always preferable than treatment, not just in Malaysia but globally. The three main categories of health awareness are physical health, mental health, and emotional health (Daria Przybylska, 2014). Health education is also important to promote improved physical and mental stability. For instance, if a person has cancer, depression—which results from being unaware of health—may also enter that person's life. Some people are totally negligent; they are unaware of their obligations, and some husbands treat their wives as their servants. Despite the fact that these people don't have any recognised diseases, they cannot be regarded as healthy (Cohrdes, Caroline, and Elvira Mauz, 2020). Considering that a healthy population would live longer and be more productive, health awareness is also important for economic development. A condition of wellbeing known as positive mental and physical health occurs when a person is aware of their own potential, able to deal with everyday pressures, able to work successfully and fruitfully, and able to give back to their community (World Health Organization, 2001). Given that health information is one of the most searched for topics online, it is reasonable to assume that the usage of social media is having an increasing impact on how health information is provided to and accessible by end users. 2020 (Gimenez-Perez et al.). Since video-assisted learning has shown to be beneficial for patients and medical students in acquiring new information, YouTube holds potential as a resource for health education (El-Jawahri A Et al, 2016).

One of the sites with the fastest growth rates is YouTube, which, according to an analysis of the Internet's top sites, ranks second during rush hour. An illustration. Since its launch in early 2005, YouTube has emerged as the most popular Internet platform offering a new generation of short video sharing services (Cheng, Dale and Liu, 2013). In this way, creating networks for traffic and sustaining their improvement depend on having a solid understanding of the features of YouTube

and similar video sharing websites. An individual who enjoys travelling should take care to prepare by becoming conscious of their health and learning about new locations. When a person like to travel, the preparation that need to care is a health awareness before going to travel and the information of new place. The significance of thorough preparation ahead to travel necessitates receiving adequate information from qualified healthcare providers, as well as the necessary immunizations and drugs.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study's primary objective is to investigate the YouTube platform's commercial health awareness deliverables to Malaysian tourists. The study makes the claim that by looking at aspects including YouTube usage, the platform's influence, and the value of health awareness videos for travelers. The advantages and disadvantages of health awareness videos have also been researched in this study in addition to the usage aspects and effects of YouTube. YouTube is the largest platform for producing, disseminating, and discovering video content in this study. Over a billion users have used YouTube recommendations to find personalised content from a constantly expanding library of videos. The significant impact that deep learning has recently had on the YouTube video recommendations system will be the main topic of this essay (Paul Covington, 2016). As of right moment, the primary mechanism for providing both instruction and entertainment is YouTube. This technology will aid in the distribution of health awareness videos to the general public, particularly in Malaysia.

2.1. Health Awareness

Today's global spread of rapid urbanisation helps emerging nations' economies thrive, but it also has a number of negative repercussions, including pollution, poverty, and health problems. According to Mazlina Mansor (*, 2014), urbanisation has the impact of increasing rural residents' migration to urban areas. In order to ensure that we have a higher quality of life and can survive, our health is also crucial. The people will benefit from this health knowledge by being more cautious about their health and avoiding dangerous diseases when they travel. For instance, when planning a trip, one should ensure that the necessary health preparations are made and one should pack one's medication to avoid accidents. Additionally, the YouTube video that serves as the primary platform for health awareness for this study's purposes is very helpful for the general population in terms of their knowledge of health awareness prior to travel.

The hypothesis of (Naseer et al, 2021) states that the significance of health education has also been acknowledged as one of the key variables that define the long-term health policy, which may indirectly be reflected in the decrease of healthcare expenditures. Preventive and instructional components of healthcare have received an increasing amount of attention in recent years. In the structure created in this way, family medicine, which is the origin of forming health-oriented attitudes, occupies a significant position. Patients believe that health information is better and most trustworthy when it comes from medical experts. An individual from Malaysia who is travelling will be better prepared with the help of this knowledge. It is essential to acquire the required information from qualified healthcare providers before travelling, as well as the necessary immunizations and prescriptions.

2.2. The Health Awareness by Video (YouTube)

Health education improves knowledge and skills related to health and illness, as well as the prevention of illness and coping with challenging circumstances. It also raises awareness and improves one's capacity to make decisions about one's health. As awareness of social, political,

and environmental variables affecting health grows, so does the range of information and expertise regarding how to use healthcare effectively (Al-Marroof, R. et. al, 2021). Because they will be aware of ways to avoid contracting an illness when travelling to another country, the public's increased health knowledge will have a good effect. They can locate a health awareness film on YouTube before their trip and access it from anywhere at any time. Furthermore, any film promoting health awareness may now be easily found on YouTube, providing information to any Malaysian traveller. The surroundings, the weather, and the social interactions in the destination should all be considered by the general public.

Before embarking on a journey, travelers should prepare their bodies and their medications by learning about the local climate and environment. For instance, if the environment is unfavourable for health, individuals will be more likely to fall ill and have poor physical health if they have not made any preparations. Moreover, while from the perspective of public health, such intervention may not be viewed favorably, the tourist may desire maximum protection and be prepared to pay for protection against contagious diseases (Leder et. al., 2015). For amusement and education, YouTube is simple to use and accessible to access. To distinguish between candidates with high recall's relative importance, the presentation of a few of the "best" recommendations in a list necessitates a fine-level representation. The ranking network completes this task by determining each video's score in accordance with a desired goal function utilising a wealth of features that describe the user and the video (Paul Covington, 2016). This element contributes to YouTube having the most users globally. In addition, YouTube, which has a commercial application and a global user base, is the greatest medium for travelers to use to find their health awareness videos before they fly. Another popular website in the world for delivering fresh content is YouTube.

Despite having a significant impact on Internet traffic in the present, YouTube itself is struggling with scalability (Hota, Soma., 2018). According to this study, leveraging YouTube for commercial purposes is the most crucial component for spreading health awareness among the populace. Communities and groups are further enabled by the social network that already exists on YouTube because users and videos are no longer separate entities. The popularity of YouTube and other comparable websites has greatly benefited from this (Burgess, Jean, and Joshua Green, 2018). The videos might be created by the traveler themselves, educating others.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study's primary objective is to investigate the YouTube platform's commercial health awareness deliverable to Malaysian tourists. The study makes the claim that by looking at aspects including YouTube usage, the platform's influence, and the value of health awareness videos for travelers. The study also looked at the benefits and drawbacks of health awareness videos in addition to factors affecting YouTube usage and impact. Male and female residents of Shah Alam, Selangor, between the ages of 15 and 45 make up the sample for this study. The fundamental premise behind the sample's selection is that all of these people are regular users of new media sites like YouTube and engage in frequent communication there.

The questionnaire is made up of three major sections which collect data on the respondents' demographic profile, their exposure to YouTube, and their knowledge about health awareness video. Due to the diversity of Malaysian citizens, the questionnaire is created to support both English and Malay speaking respondents. The data and responses collected from the sample are further analysed and discussed in the subsequent chapter, in which the findings of this study are presented. Through these findings, this study will be able to discover the various relationships between factors of usage involvement with health awareness video, and the impact of YouTube

towards health awareness video and understand if there are any dire consequences between these relationships.

4. FINDINGS AND DATA ANALYSIS

There are findings and analysis that can be used for this purpose of this research. To find the data in this research, the result from a via Goggle Form survey was finalized and analyzed with using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software. Followed by next step is to put the data in reliability of data to find the reliability of this research and the important part is the most and valid Cronbach's alpha 0.952 which is quite highest but still good for this test. Next, based on the findings in this research, in terms through of mean and standard deviation, it shows YouTube can make traveller feel more interested in learning about health awareness is a highest agree by the respondents. Lastly, for data analysis and hypothesis the result show has been rejected there is a significant difference between the impacts of YouTube as a health awareness video to traveler from Malaysia and factor of usage in YouTube video of health awareness for traveler from Malaysia.

As we can see in the following Table 1, the table show how the impact of YouTube to respondent gives a different perspective to them when used it in daily life. This also show the difference of factors of usage of YouTube as a main application in terms of search of any related video of health awareness before travelling. According to results also shows, there are many significant differences between the impact of YouTube and factors of usage of YouTube between difference range of age. Besides that, a statement that agree by respondent for "I think YouTube will help traveller better understand about health awareness in terms of taking precautions" also, but this was not the highest mean point with 4.1333. For general knowledge, respondent needs to know the precautions how to take an awareness about their health like checkup or take anything supplements. With this precaution, they can prevent than anything can affect them while travelling.

Next, for the statement which is "It is very convenient to use YouTube because it is not a compulsory for everyone to sign up an account" and this is an advantage for respondent to use a YouTube as their main application for find any related video about health awareness. Besides that, respondents have their option to choose any platform to use find a material about health awareness without YouTube application. With this statement, it shows how respondents care about the some of features about certain application when they used it for any purpose.

Table 1. The Impacts of YouTube As A Health Awareness Video to Traveler from Malaysia.

SECTION B	Mean	Standard Deviation
B1. I think YouTube has makes me realize to take precautions before travelling.	3.8444	1.12726
B4. I think YouTube is a great platform to learn any tips regarding health awareness before travelling.	4.1333	.91949
B6. I think knowing the precautions that need to be taken before travelling will be more attractive by using YouTube.	4.0000	.92932
B7. I think health awareness videos in YouTube can be easily accessed.	4.0889	1.06221
B.10. I think YouTube can make traveller feel more interested in learning about health awareness.	4.1556	.79646
C1. I think YouTube is easy to use because it has variety of features (e.g. free usage, video upload).	4.2889	.81526
C4. I think YouTube will help traveller better understand about health awareness in terms of taking precautions.	4.1333	1.09959
C8. I think YouTube does not require many storage when user download videos in their smartphones.	3.6889	1.08339
C9. I think watching videos on YouTube is more interesting as I can also scroll through other people's comments.	4.1556	.92823

5. CONCLUSIONS

YouTube application nowadays actually monopoly in this technology arena. This application helps a lot in terms many ways for example to learn something new without have any difficulties. Based on the research, the impacts of YouTube as a health awareness video to traveler from Malaysia give an impact to respondents on how they use a YouTube as a main application to find any materials for health awareness before travelling. This supported based on the results in Table 1 on how the respondent prefer a YouTube as their first application to surf any video regarding health awareness.

After a using a YouTube as a main platform to find any related video about health awareness, the respondents agree with a many feature provided by YouTube is attract them to use that application. These statements proven by Table 4.8 in questions C1 that mention about the features provided by a YouTube. Meanwhile, personally from the researcher also agree with a YouTube as a main platform to find any precautions about health awareness video or materials. With this research, it makes a clear statement which is the impacts of YouTube as a health awareness video to traveler from Malaysia affected a respondent to agree with this research questions. Followed by factor of usage in YouTube video of health awareness for traveler from Malaysia.

This research found that based on the impacts of YouTube as a health awareness video to traveller from Malaysia gives good positive impact like gives advantages for traveller to gain more knowledge before travelling and this supported and prove by in Table 1 in questions B4. Also, with this result, most of respondents agreed with this statement which is it will add some knowledge in terms precaution of health awareness before travelling. In addition, the impacts of YouTube as a health awareness video to traveller from Malaysia affecting people to use a YouTube as a main of application and to fulfills the need of importance of social life cycle.

Future studies indicate that everyone who lives in the technological age of today has several advantages. The explanation is based on the fact that in this day and age, people choose to use a

variety of applications to obtain any entertainment or educational reasons through internet platforms. One of the most well-liked examples is a YouTube application. In addition, YouTube has become a forum for educating people on all aspects of life. This study primarily examines the effects of YouTube as a resource for health awareness videos for travelers from Malaysia as well as the factors that influence their use. There are other studies of this type, but this one is particularly focused on how to check for health awareness through YouTube application.

In addition, there are a number of recommendations that a researcher can offer to someone in the same field about how to persuade individuals to upload more videos on health awareness to YouTube and how to improve the appeal of that content to draw in more viewers, particularly tourists from Malaysia. This is so that other communities can receive accurate information about health awareness before travel. Additionally, in order to avoid running out of time, planning in terms of times and work progress must balance for the new researcher doing a research project. A good plan will be carried out at the proper time and pace to guarantee that everything will proceed according to schedule. But the key to making sure that planning goes successfully is to give yourself enough time to prepare and to avoid being caught in one place.

In order to draw a conclusion from this research study, it is crucial to consider how this research will affect how everyone knows about the YouTube platform's delivery as a commercial health awareness to Malaysian travelers. In addition, this study discovered outcomes that are in line with the study's aims and research question and have received positive comments. In terms of assisting Malaysian travelers in locating any resources, such as videos about health awareness before travelling and providing fresh knowledge about health awareness, YouTube can be a valuable resource. Additionally, YouTube has a significant impact on application websites, attracting users to utilising them as a platform to find videos and create content for them. In addition, most people in Malaysia like to find a health awareness video in a YouTube application and use to be their preference to add some knowledge for them.

Lastly, with a YouTube platform as deliverable of commercial health awareness video, traveller from Malaysia will get a positive benefit without doubt to use this application anymore. However, people in Malaysia must know the right information to use because some of another people like to take this advantage to produce a wrong information regarding health awareness video in YouTube application.

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